

DESI and Mayall: Ready for Adventure

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Now equipped with the ground-breaking Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (DESI; <https://www.desi.lbl.gov>), the Nicholas U. Mayall 4m Telescope is about to embark on a new voyage of discovery. DESI can now deliver simultaneous spectra of nearly 5000 targets spread over a 3-degree-diameter field of view in a single exposure and can acquire new fields within minutes. The DESI project, funded by the U.S. Department of Energy Office of Science and led by the Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, and involving an international team from 75 institutions spread over 13 nations, will revolutionize our understanding of the cosmos and shed light on its darkest and most mysterious component—the dark energy that pervades the Universe and is responsible for its accelerating expansion.

The Mayall telescope was taken out of service in February 2018 in order to perform various upgrades and install the DESI instrument. The process involved installing on the Mayall telescope structure a new top end ring capable of supporting the barrel containing the new prime focus optics, the DESI focal plane holding the 5000 robotic fiber positioners, and roughly 1 million feet of fiber-optic cable. In addition, a thermal enclosure was installed in the old coude room and equipped with ten 3-arm spectrographs covering the optical wavelength range 360–980nm with a (blue-to-red) resolution of 2800–5000. The Mayall's Cassegrain cage now holds an upward-looking fiber-view camera, capable of imaging the 5000 fibers (when back illuminated) and precisely measuring their relative positions. A new control room was constructed and equipped on the U-floor of the Mayall building. The installation was completed in fall 2019, and the instrument saw first light on 22 October 2019.

DESI was fully commissioned over the following five months. The instrument can now efficiently position fibers with ~ 0.1 arcsec accuracy with high reliability and repeat-

Figure 1: The Mayall telescope at the Kitt Peak National Observatory is poised to undertake the largest cosmic cartography project in history. (Credit: LBNL/DoE/M. Chung)

Figure 2: The DESI focal plane, with 5000 robotic fiber positioners, has the largest grasp of any multi-object spectroscopic instrument ever built. (Credit: LBNL/DoE/R. Besuner)

ability. The team successfully obtained some science data in early March before shutting down operations (and placing the instrument in a safe state) in response to the COVID-19 pandemic.

The DESI collaboration is busy actively analyzing science data and working to improve the project's operational and data processing capabilities. Over the course of the commissioning campaign, DESI collected spectra of around 0.7 million unique targets! Despite the untimely cessation of operations, the DESI project successfully passed the Department of Energy's construction completion review with flying colors. The instrument is now ready for its new mission—which will resume when the Observatory restarts operations sometime in fall 2020.

Over its five-year mission, DESI will measure the redshifts of 35 million galaxies and quasars, with the goal of producing the most precise measurement of the expansion

Figure 3: Images from the Legacy Surveys and sample spectra obtained with DESI in March 2020. The image panels, 66 arcseconds on a side, show false-color grz images with the target in the center. The spectra show examples of a bright galaxy, a luminous red galaxy, two emission line galaxies, a quasar, and an unusual white dwarf – M-star binary. The wavelength scale is in Angstroms, and the flux density scale is in nanomaggies. (Credit: DESI Collaboration)

history of the Universe and the best constraints on the equation of state of dark energy to date. DESI will also measure the velocities of many millions of Milky Way stars and explore the dynamical and chemical formation history of our Galaxy's halo and disk. DESI's targets will be chosen from the large public imaging dataset produced by the Legacy Surveys (<http://legacysurvey.org>). The combination of the imaging and spectroscopic data will provide an invaluable resource for answering a wide range of astrophysical questions.

We look forward to restarting operations and reopening the DESI data floodgates soon. The Universe awaits ...